

The Legends of a lost civilization – The Prachi Valley

Sarita Dash

*Ph.D Research Scholar
Mumbai University*

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Abstract

Southeast India that covers a vast extensive area between the two mighty rivers- the Ganga and Godavari, is hemmed with thick clad of jungle, mountainous ranges, and at the east by the sea, forms an ideal ground which makes an unique history of its own. This region, which was known as Utkal or Odra, now better known as Odisha. Right from its past, the people of Odisha have played significant role in the cultural and political ferments of the whole country as the Hindu period was longest in this reason and the dynasties that ruled the area were all long lived and sufficiently strong to maintain the integrity of this geographical unit. Odisha, thus possessing a rich culture, once cradled a civilization which was varied in character, glorified the entire land. This civilization famous as the Prachi Valley Civilization that flourished on the bank of river Prachi was considered as the holiest river of Odisha. This civilization has everything that makes the history of Odisha most outstanding and glorious. Though the origin of Prachi is still wrapped in mystery, legends, as embodied in different Puranas take the sanctity of this civilization to mythical times. This paper aims highlighting the legendary stories of the valley that played an important role in making the history of Odisha. Recorded events and traditional accounts also are excellent elements of history. However, bizarre and incredulous they might look, they certainly contain some germs of truth, and the distilled wisdom of ages cannot be ignored for which we have incorporated them at several places, sometimes without examining their authenticity.

Keywords: Civilization, mystery, legendary stories, bizarre, authenticity.

Southeast India that covers a vast extensive area between the two mighty rivers- the Ganga and Godavari, is hemmed with thick clad of jungle, mountainous ranges, and at the east by the sea, forms an ideal ground which makes a unique history of its own. This area as known by different names since ancient times as Utkal, Kalinga, Trikalika, Kosala, Odra, Orissa (as it's Anglicized form) and now at present being called as Odisha. The land of Orissa underwent a major cultural transformation with the influx of Aryan culture from north and the Dravidian from south. Consequently, the traditional Orissan culture prior to Islamic and western influence developed into mainly a synthesis of tribal, Aryan and Dravidian culture.

Most of the great civilizations of the world have originated and flourished on river valleys. Like other great civilizations, Odisha too had many geographical tracts on the banks of rivers that have ancient civilization vestiges. One such civilization was Prachi valley civilization. It was the holiest river of Odisha that makes its (Prachi Valley) history most outstanding and glorious. Even though the Prachi is a small river compared to the Mahanadi, Brahmini, Subarnarekha and Baitarani, it has the remnants of one of the most glorious civilization with a magnificent past. Believed to be one of the oldest and most sacred rivers of Odisha, Prachi today is just a small tributary of the Mahanadi. The source of this ancient river can be traced to Dakamba near Naraj of Cuttack district. It flowed through the coastal region of the undivided Puri district before it merges in the Bay of Bengal by way of two bifurcations, one at Astarang and the other near Konark (Dhir, 2018).

Thus, the Prachi valley Civilization plays an important role in making of Odisha. Right from the period, when the primitive people chose to settle down on the soil of Odisha, this valley was proved to be a veritable chosen land which offered them fertile plain for agriculture, rivers for irrigation and navigation and sprawling pastures for cattle rearing. When the civilization marched ahead with the growth of inter-relationship, mutual acceptance of culture and mutual benefit, inflow and outflow of races and trade relationship, the history of this region interwoven with multi-dimensional events, was richer enough, to build up a distinct and different story without the knowledge of which any research in the realm of Odishan history seems to be incomplete and infructuous.

The need to write regional histories with a view to strengthening the common cohesive factor among the people of our country and to offer information for the complication of a better and rational history was very much felt by our post-colonial historians. The scope of history is not confined to show only a procession of dynasties and to record the genealogical tables. Its scope

certainly transcends them all. It seeks to show the life of the common people, their aspirations and achievements, their beliefs and traditions, their sufferings and failures and many things of like nature.

Recorded events and traditional accounts also are excellent elements of history. However, bizarre and incredulous they might look, they certainly contain some germs of truth and the distilled wisdom of ages cannot be ignored for which we have incorporated them at several places, sometimes without examining their authenticity.

For example, everybody knows through the recorded history, that Odisha unlike many other parts of India has an uninterrupted series of temples, illustrating the history of the well-defined Kalinga order from its very inception to decline. And Sun temple of Konark marks the highest point of achievements of that order. Konark a small village in the Puri district of Odisha, 3Kms away of the Bay of Bengal has its name derived from the name of the presiding deity Konark, The Sun. The main temple was by early European miners as the “Black Pagoda” in contradiction to the white Pagoda (the whitewashed temple of Jagannath) of Puri, both important landmarks in their coastal voyage. Even in its present ruined state (as it lost its soaring tower long ago), it stands in majestic dignity in the midst of a vast stretch of sand and desolate solitude which further emphasize its greatness. Architecture and sculpture go hand in hand in Indian temples, but both have a total concept at the sun temple. The stupendous size of the temple, that is filled with endless wealth of decoration on its body, which includes the minute patterns to the boldly carved modeled free-standing sculptures of exceptionally large size, shows its architectural beauty (Mitra, 1992).

History has also recorded, the entire genealogical table of the Ganga dynasty and the brilliant achievements of the King Narasimha Deva, the builder of the Konark temple. It was only through his unstinted effort such a massive edifice was built in the Prachi Valley. But little is known about the real builder, the chief architect and minister (Patra) Sibeisantara and his initial trials and tribulations. Once reprimanded by the king for his initial failures in executing the temple plan at the foundation level he slipped away secretly to the Prachi forest and roamed aimlessly as a disheartened soul. Unable to bear the pains of hunger, he reached the nearest home, occupied by the sole owner, an old lady and asked her for some food. The old lady without knowing his identity took pity on him and prepared some rice gruel and offered him for his meal. Without waiting for a while to let the gruel to let it cool, Sibeisantara dipped his hand at the middle of the saucer. The simmering hot gruel burnt his fingers. Alarmed at his foolishness the old woman blurted out, “Don’t behave like Sibeisantara”. Being unable to understand the exact implication of his words, the Chief Architect asked to explain the mistakes of Sibeisantara. She told that Sibeisantara was all along in a hurry and began to plunge his hand at the middle of this temple plan without perfecting the initial stage at the foundation. When Sibeisantara disclosed his identity, the

old lady advised him to have patience, and to slow down with his temple plan, perfect his style with a model temple first before proceeding with the construction of the Konark Temple.

He constructed the model temple under the guidance of the old lady. The temple was named as Trilochanesvara temple at the village Shadansa which is five miles north of the Madhava temple. This stone temple though in small size perfectly anticipates the construction of the Konarak temple, but now, very little about the temple is known to the outsiders. Even then we feel Sibi Santara went wrong with his plan because both the temples (vimana) collapsed at the verandah level almost simultaneously. (Tripathi, 1987)

There are several opinions by various historians about the demolition of this magnificent temple. Some say that the Muslim invader Kalapahada was responsible for its demolition, while others say that it was never completed or that it collapsed due to overgrowth of trees or even that pirates took away the magnet which was fixed at the pinnacle (high point) and held the entire temple in perfect balance, does not seem convincing. However, it may be opined that the hurried haste with which these two temples were constructed proved fatal and for that matter the king's constant threat to behead architects unless they finished the construction within the stipulated period of 12 years was chiefly responsible for the defective plan.

Apart from this legend, there are other legends from Prachi Valley which tell us about the construction, existence as well as origin of the temple. These legends as embodied in the Kapila Samhita, the Madala Panji (chronicle of the Jagannath temple, Puri) and the Prachi Mahatmya, take the sanctity of Konark back to its mythical times. The most interesting legend is the story of Dharmapada, a small boy of 12 years who belonged to a small village of Prachi Valley. Here is the narrative of the legend of Dharmapada. Long ago, King Narashimhadev I employed the Divine Architect, Bisu Maharana, to construct the Konarak temple. For astrological reasons both the selection of the site of the temple (at the location near the Bay of Bengal) and the timing and nature of the construction had to be exact (1200 artisans working alone and in isolation must build the temple in exactly 12 yrs). According to the conditions set by the king, the risk of failure to complete the project as per stipulations would be the execution of the entire work force. The Divine Architect Bisu Maharana, confident of his ability and the skills of his 1200 artisans, took up the challenge and thus left his family behind for 12 years and he and his workmen went into isolation at the remote construction site.

On the night before his departure the Divine Architect's wife became pregnant and nine months later she gave birth to a son. The son, Dharmapada, was a genius who quickly and easily mastered all the books in the family library. He was so to be called as the Mozart of Architecture. He grew up hearing majestic tales about his great faith in Divine Architect. He longed to meet his adored yet absent father, but of course that was forbidden by the orders and conditions of the King. Nearly 12 years went by before his mother allowed him to leave the family home and

venture off to seek his father at the distant temple site by the sea. As he set off on his journey to Konark, Dharmapada's mother gave the boy two marks of family identity to carry with him so that his father would recognize him: her wedding ring and a distinctive fruit from the family garden.

After a long walk, Dharmapada arrives at the construction site and sees the grand sun temple. He also sees several of the artisans. Much to his surprise they were hopeless. They told him that the temple was complete except the final key stone or the Kalash (capstone), which keep falling off. There is a mysterious and disastrous problem with the design of the temple which the Divine Architect has been unable to fix or even detect. Unless the problem could not be solved by midnight all of them, including the Divine Architect, would be executed by the king.

The boy walked around the temple and quickly spotted a minor and easily corrected flaw. "Take me to the tent of the Divine Architect" he exclaimed! The artisans brought the boy to the tent where Bisu Maharana was going out of his mind trying to figure out what went wrong. "This boy says he can fix the temple", the artisans announced, thereby sending the divine architect into a rage over the arrogance of a child presuming to telling him how to design a temple. He dragged the boy by the ear to the temple site. The boy pointed to the flaw, which the divine architect immediately recognized and then rectified. The capstone was successfully placed on the temple and the work was completed in time.

At first there was a great celebration of success but then slowly an anxious and dreadful science fell over the crowd of artisans. One of the men approached the divine architect and said "It is great that we have completed the temple in time but if the king finds out that we have done this with the help of this boy he will kill us anyway since total number of artisans becomes twelve hundred or one. There is but one way out of this dilemma. The boy must be killed; and since you are our leader and the divine architect, you must kill him". "But he is an innocent child," the divine architect averred, horrified by the proposal. "Never the less sir, it remains twelve hundred or one". The spokesman for the artisans tried to impress him about the inexorable utilitarian moral calculation and urged him to kill the boy. Reluctantly the divine architect agreed to end the life of the one person so that the lives of the twelve hundred might be saved.

Night time arrived. With blade in hand, Bisu Maharana entered Dharmapada's tent intending to kill him. Standing over the boy's bed he slowly raises the knife and is about to slay the sleeping child when he noticed the wedding ring and the fruit from the family garden. He immediately realized that this brilliant boy was his son. He awakened Dharmapada and embraced him with joy and tears. Finally, father and son were united after a long period.

The divine architect, together with Dharmapada, approached the twelve hundred artisan who were waiting outside the tent. He announced to all "This is my son Dharmapada". The divine

architect was very proud to tell the other artisans about his son, anticipating a great celebration. But the twelve hundred artisans remained unmoved even after the discovery and said to the divine architect, “a moment ago when you did not know the precise identity of this boy you were willing to kill him to save us all. Now you are trying to save him because he happens to be your son. Be consistent. What difference does it make if he is your son? The fact is that it is still twelve hundred and one!”

Listening to this the divine architect became stunned and became downed with moral dilemma. Dharmapada observing the helpless condition of his father asked him “are you for the twelve hundred artisans or are you for your son?” Bisu- Maharana was very upset about this. Dharmapada on seeing his helpless father, requested him to have a view of the site, he had knowledge about the construction from the manuscript and knew the manuscript and knew the design of the stone that would fit as the key stone and hold the temple together, he explained everything to his father, who was so surprised and felt proud to have such a talented son. Bisu was very happy with his son who saved their lives. The people started whispering that the king would even then kill all the architects, as the “Kalash” was erected by a 12-year-old child. Hearing this, Dharmapada touched his father’s feet and climbed the top of the “Kalash” and looked at the horizon with tears and jumped off into the deep blue sea. This young boy who achieved the ultimate glory of Odissan art and architecture by completing the greatest temple now lives in the folklore and in the aspirations of every young craftsman of the region (Mitra, 1992).

. Although the river Prachi is dead now, it is considered as one of the oldest civilizations that survived the ravages of time. Though the origin of Prachi is still wrapped in mystery, legends, as embodied in different Puranas take the sanctity of this civilization to mythical times. The legendary stories of the valley played an important role in making the history of Odisha. Recorded events and traditional accounts also are excellent elements of history. Whatever bizarre and incredulous they might look, they certainly contain some germs of truth. And the distilled wisdom of ages cannot be ignored for which these legends and lores have been incorporated at several places, sometimes without examining their authenticity.

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